

Identification and Pathogenicity of Fungi Causing Postharvest Decay of Irish Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) Tubers Sold in Makurdi

A.O. Fayinminu

Department of Biological Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

K. Liamngee

Department of Biological Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

T. Gbira

Bioresources Development Centre (BIODEC), Makurdi, Nigeria

N.G. Fru

Centre for Food Technology and Research (CEFTER), Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Y. Rekiya

Bioresources Development Centre (BIODEC), Makurdi, Nigeria

A. Mohammad

Bioresources Development Centre (BIODEC), Makurdi, Nigeria

A.B. Kum

Faculty of Agriculture, St Louis University Institute, Littoral Region, Cameroon

L.W. Mbateng

Centre for Food Technology and Research (CEFTER), Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

T.G. Ligom

Centre for Food Technology and Research (CEFTER), Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

D.T. Awua

Department of Biological Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Abstract

Irish potato tubers production has suffered greatly due to pre and postharvest attack of pathogens on the crop. A study was carried out to identify fungi organisms causing postharvest decay of Irish potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) tubers in Makurdi. Irish potato tubers showing symptoms of decay were obtained from four markets in Makurdi namely; North Bank, High Level, Wadata and Wurukum. The Irish potato tubers were taken to the Botany Laboratory of the Benue State University for isolation of fungi pathogens. *Small sections were cut from decaying tubers and surface sterilized in 5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution for 1 minute and rinsed in several changes of sterile distilled water.* The pathogenicity of the isolated fungi was also carried out on healthy Irish potato tubers. Data were analyzed using analysis of variance at 95% level of significance and means were separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference. Three fungi were isolated namely; *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp. and *Fusarium* sp. Results showed that fungi occurrence recorded at Wurukum (7.67) was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) compared with NorthBank (5.50), High Level (4.63) and Wadata (2.20) respectively. There was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the occurrence of specific fungi across the markets. Occurrence of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Bipolaris* sp. was significantly higher in North Bank with 5.77% and 4.20% respectively compared with other fungi while occurrence of *Fusarium* sp. was significantly higher in Wurukum 5.27% compared with other fungi organisms. The area of rot induced by *Bipolaris* sp (8.10)cm² was significantly higher compared with *Fusarium* sp.

(7.43)cm², *Aspergillus flavus* (6.30)cm² and control (0.00)cm². Irish potato tubers in Makurdi are contaminated with fungi and these isolated fungi are capable of replicating the same disease condition in healthy Irish potato tubers. Therefore, Irish potato tubers with symptoms of decay should not be consumed and good hygienic practices should be employed by farmers and sellers to avoid inoculum transmission to produce after harvest.

Keywords: *Irish potato, postharvest decay, isolation, fungi, pathogenicity.*

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Introduction

Solanum tuberosum (L), commonly known as the Irish potato, is a tuberous crop belonging to the Solanaceae family. Ranking fourth globally in production, it surpasses only maize, rice, and wheat (Food and Agriculture Organization Statistics; FAOSTAT, 2016). Originating in South America, this non-cereal crop plays a vital role in food security, particularly in developing countries (Zhang *et al.*, 2016). The global production of Irish potatoes reaches approximately 388 million metric tonnes, with an average yield of 20,110.8 kg/ha. Developing countries account for over 50% of this output, while China and India collectively produce one-third. China leads global production with 99 million metric tonnes (FAOSTAT, 2019). In Africa, Irish potato production totals 25 million metric tonnes.

Africa's Irish potato production is led by Algeria, with an output of 4,606,400 metric tonnes, followed closely by Egypt (4,325,480 metric tonnes) and South Africa (2,450,540 metric tonnes). Nigeria ranks seventh, producing 1,284,370 metric tonnes, trailing Morocco (1,924,870 metric tonnes), Tanzania (1,749,201 metric tonnes), and Kenya (FAOSTAT, 2019). Nigeria's introduction to Irish potato occurred in the 19th Century, specifically in the Jos Plateau region (Tadesse *et al.*, 2018). Plateau State's climate, characterized by average temperatures of 31.7°C (max) and 15°C (min), facilitates optimal Irish potato cultivation. The region experiences a rainy season (April-October) and a dry season (November-February), with temperatures peaking in March-May and dipping in December-January. Beyond Jos Plateau, Nigerian regions conducive to Irish potato production include Zaria (Kaduna), Mambila (Taraba), Obudu (Cross River), and parts of Nsukka (Enugu). This versatile crop has significant economic value, serving multiple purposes. Its uses encompass fresh consumption, processing into various products (snacks, fries, crisps), and utilization as a food ingredient. Additionally, Irish potatoes are employed in non-food applications, such as industrial starch, animal feed, adhesive production, and seed tubers.

Statement of the Problem

Irish potato tubers, like other crops, are susceptible to various pathogens, including fungi, bacteria, and viruses, resulting in significant disease-related constraints. Post-harvest spoilage is the most pressing issue, with substantial losses occurring during storage and handling. According to International Institute of Postharvest Engineering and Technology; ICAR-CIPHET (2015), up to 15% of fresh produce is lost at the post-harvest stage. Moreover, poor storage conditions lead to 10-40% decay of harvested potato roots, with developing countries experiencing even higher losses (Cerioni *et al.*, 2013). Notably, potato roots suffer the greatest losses from disease attack worldwide. Fungi such as *Rhizoctonia bataticola*, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, *Fusarium redolens*, *F. oxysporum*, *Penicillium* species and *Rhizopus oryzae* were associated with post-harvest rot of Irish potato tubers in south-east and south-west, Nigeria (Ezeonu *et*

al., 2019). Certain *Fusarium* species are responsible for causing dry rot in Irish potato tubers. This contamination leads to the production of mycotoxins, which pose significant health risks to humans and animals. The mycotoxins exhibit cytotoxic, hepatotoxic, and neurotoxic effects, making infected tubers hazardous for direct consumption or indirect exposure through animal products (e.g., milk, meat) from animals fed contaminated feed (Emil *et al.*, 2016).

Significance of the Study

The findings from this study will benefit various stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, processors, consumers, and plant science students. Specifically, farmers and processors will gain insights into good agricultural practices to minimize fungal contamination, ensuring high-quality potato roots with extended shelf life. Students will utilize this research as a reference point for literature reviews, while consumers will become informed about the risks associated with consuming infected Irish potato tubers.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of the research is to isolate and identify fungi causing postharvest decay of Irish potato tubers in Makurdi.

The set objectives are to;

- i. Isolate and identify fungi organisms causing postharvest decay of Irish potato tubers in Makurdi and test their pathogenicity.
- ii. Determine the occurrence of fungi and individual fungi on decaying Irish potato tubers from major markets in Makurdi.
- iii. Describe the features of the rot induced on healthy Irish potato tubers.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Location

The study was carried out in the Botany Laboratory of Department of Biological sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi.

Collection of Irish Potato Tubers

Tubers of Irish potatoes showing symptoms of decay were obtained from four markets in Makurdi namely: High Level, Northbank, Wadata and Wurukum markets. The Irish potato tubers were packaged in polyethylene bags, labeled properly and carried to the Botany Laboratory of Benue State University, Makurdi where assessments of fungal pathogens causing the decay were isolated.

Media Preparation

For fungal pathogen isolation, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) medium was utilized, prepared according to manufacturer guidelines. About 62.0g powdered SDA was dissolved in 1000ml sterile distilled water, stirred vigorously, and heated until clear. The solution was autoclaved at 121°C for 15min at 760mm/Hg. Streptomycin sulphate (2-3 drops) was added to inhibit bacterial growth. After cooling, the medium was poured into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify before fungal culturing.

Isolation of fungal from decaying Irish Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.)

Irish potato tubers exhibiting decay were dissected using a sterile knife. Diseased tissue was extracted from the advancing rot with sterile forceps (Agu *et al.*, 2015). The excised tissue underwent surface sterilization in 5% sodium hypochlorite solution for 30 seconds to 1 minute, followed by rinsing in sterile

distilled water (three changes) and drying on filter paper (5 minutes). The sterilized tissue was then cultured on solidified Sabouraud Dextrose Agar in 9cm Petri dishes, incubated at ambient temperature (5-7 days) with daily observations for fungal growth. After 5-7 days of growth, sub-culturing was done to obtain pure cultures of the isolates. The data collected include:

Percentage occurrence of fungi

Plates were observed for growth and the occurrence of fungi was determined by counting the number of fungi per market divided by the total number of fungi and expressed as a percentage using the formula adopted by Zakawa *et al.* (2018).

$$\frac{\text{Number of fungi per market}}{\text{Total number of fungi}} \times 10 \quad (1)$$

Percentage occurrence of individual Fungi

Plates were observed for growth and the occurrence of individual fungi was determined by counting the number of times each individual fungus occurred divided by the total number of fungi per plate and expressed as a percentage using the formula adopted by Liamngee *et al.* (2016).

$$\frac{\text{Number of times each fungus occurred}}{\text{Total number of fungi per plate}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Subculturing of Fungi Isolates

To subculture, a sterilized inoculation needle was used to pick a little quantity of the fungal growth on the old culture and transferred to the centre of a freshly prepared SDA in another Petri dish. Sub-culturing was done repeatedly until pure culture of each fungal isolate was obtained as reported by Liamngee *et al.* (2016).

Identification of Fungi

Fungal identification was conducted through macroscopic and microscopic analysis. Macroscopic examination involved observing color, growth pattern, and growth rate on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) in Petri plates. Microscopic identification entailed staining with Lactophenol cotton blue, inoculating a fungal colony onto a glass slide, and examining under a 40× objective lens light microscope. Observed characteristics were compared to Barnett and Hunter's (1972) standard chart, as cited by Liamngee *et al.* (2016), for accurate identification.

Pathogenicity of Fungal Isolates on Healthy Irish Potato Tubers in Makurdi

Pathogenicity testing was conducted on healthy Irish potato tubers using pure cultures of fungal isolates from diseased Irish potato tubers. Okigbo and Okediugwu (2000) method was employed. Briefly, 5mm holes were created in Irish potato tubers using a cork borer, and 5mm agar plugs from 5-7 day-old cultures were inserted. Three tubers per isolate were used. Inoculated tubers were labeled and incubated at room temperature (7-10 days). The control was Irish potato tubers treated with SDA without any organism. After 7-10 days of incubation, with the aid of a sharp knife, the margin along the decayed area of the Irish potato tubers were cut open and the lesion length and diameter were measured using a metre rule. The area of rot was calculated using the formula adopted by Ezeibekwe and Ibe (2010) as:

$$\text{Area of rot} = \pi dl \text{ (Where } \pi = 22/7, d = \text{diameter, } l = \text{depth)} \quad (3)$$

On appearance of symptoms, the portion of the diseased parts was cut, surface sterilized to remove external contaminants and placed on Potato Dextrose Agar for re-isolation and the morphological characteristic observed were compared to the original isolates.

Description of Rot

The description of the rot induced by each fungus on the healthy Irish potato tubers were noted and documented. The nature of the rot and characteristics features were noted and described.

Data Analysis

Data obtained from this study was analyzed using Analysis of Variance and Fisher's Least Significant Difference was used to separate means.

Results

The fungi organisms isolated from decaying Irish potato tubers from this research were identified to be; *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp. and *Fusarium* sp. The appearance of these organisms on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar and under microscope is presented in Plate 1a-3b. The colony of *A. flavus* on SDA was greenish in colour (Plate 1a). When viewed under the microscope, *A. flavus* conidia was bluish green in colour with transparent conidiophores (Plate 1b). *Bipolaris* sp colonies were initially white on SDA but as days progresses becoming dark grey to blackish brown and effused (Plate 2a). The hyphae were septate and conidia were curved when viewed under the microscope (Plate 2b). The colony colour of *Fusarium* sp. started as white cottony like appearance and changed to pinkish white as days progressed on SDA (Plate 3a). When viewed under the light microscope, the conidia were hyaline with sickle cell shape (Plate 3b).

**Plate 1a. Macroscopic View of *A. flavus*.
The Colony Colour was Green**

**Plate 1b. Microscopic View of *A. flavus*.
The Conidia were Bluish Green with
Transparent Conidiophores**

Plate 2a. Macroscopic View of *Bipolaris* sp.
The Colony Colour was Dark Grey to Blackish Brown and Effuse

Plate 2b. Microscopic View of *Bipolaris* sp.
The Conidia were Curved

Plate 3a. Macroscopic View of *Fusarium* sp.
The Colony Colour was Pinkish White

Plate 3b. Microscopic View of *Fusarium* sp.
Conidia were Hyaline with Sickle Cell Shape

The percentage fungi occurrence in Irish potato obtained from four different markets in Makurdi is shown in Table 1. The fungi occurrence recorded at Wurukum (7.67) was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) compared with NorthBank (5.50), High Level (4.63) and Wadata (2.20) respectively.

**Table 1. Percentage Fungi Occurrence in Irish Potato
Obtained from Different Markets in Makurdi**

Location	Occurrence (%)
High Level	4.63

North Bank	5.50
Wadata	2.20
Wurukum	7.67
FLSD (0.05)	1.82

Key: FLSD: Fisher's Least Significant Difference

The occurrence of individual isolates from decaying Irish potato tubers in markets in Makurdi is presented in Table 2. Three fungi species were recorded namely: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp and *Fusarium* sp. There was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the occurrence of specific fungi across the markets. The percentage occurrence of *Aspergillus flavus* was higher in North Bank market with 5.77% compared with Wurukum market (4.33%), Wadata (3.67%) and High Level market with (3.56%) respectively. The percentage occurrence of *Bipolaris* sp was higher in North Bank market with 4.20% compared with High Level (4.00%), Wadata market (3.93%) and Wurukum (3.33%) having the least occurrence. The percentage occurrence of *Fusarium* sp. was higher in Wurukum (5.27%), Wadata (5.10%), NorthBank (4.33%) and High Level market with 3.67%.

Table 2. Occurrence of Individual Fungi Isolated from Irish Potato Tubers Collected from Different Markets in Makurdi

Location	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	<i>Bipolaris</i> sp	<i>Fusarium</i>
High Level	3.56	4.00	3.67
North Bank	5.77	4.20	4.33
Wadata	4.83	3.33	5.27
Wurukum	3.67	3.93	5.10
FLSD (0.05)	0.83	0.68	0.45

Key: FLSD: Fisher's Least Significant Difference

The disease-causing potentials of the isolates is shown in Table 3. All the tested organisms caused significant rot on healthy Irish potato tubers. The rot induced by *Bipolaris* sp (8.10cm²) was significantly higher on healthy Irish potato tubers, compared with rot induced by *Fusarium* sp (7.43) cm², *Aspergillus flavus* (6.30) cm² and the lowest was recorded in the uninoculated (control) (0.00) cm².

Table 3. Disease Causing Potential of Some Fungi Isolates on Healthy Irish Potato Tubers in Makurdi, Benue State

Fungi Isolate	Area of Rot (cm ²)
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	6.30
<i>Bipolaris</i> sp	8.10
<i>Fusarium</i> sp	7.43
Control	1.90
FLSD (0.05)	1.50

Key: FLSD: Fisher's Least Significant Difference

Table 4. Morphological Description of rot Induced by Isolated Fungi Organisms Inoculated on Healthy Irish Potato Tubers

Fungal Organisms	Nature of Rot
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	The rot induced was soft with brownish-green mycelia covering the region of inoculation with foam like white spores produced at the centre of inoculation. The rot spread across the internal diameter of the tuber producing an offensive odour (Plate 4)
<i>Bipolaris</i> sp	Whitish foamy mycelia covered the region of inoculation and as days progressed, turned creamish retaining foam like white spores at the centre of inoculation. The rot produced a characteristics pungent odour (Plate 5)
<i>Fusarium</i> sp	The rot started as a wound with water-soaked dull area followed by white sporulation of the fungi (Plate 6)

Plate 4. Rot caused by *Aspergillus flavus* on healthy Irish Potato tubers

Plate 5. Rot caused by *Bipolaris* sp on healthy Irish Potato tubers

Plate 6. Rot caused by *Fusarium* sp on healthy Irish Potato tubers

Discussion

Investigations in Makurdi, Nigeria, identified three fungal pathogens responsible for postharvest decay of Irish potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) tubers which are: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp., and *Fusarium* sp. These findings align with previous studies, including Salami and Popoola (2007), who reported *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Fusarium redolens*, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Penicillium* sp. as primary causal agents in Ogun State. Additionally, Muhammed *et al.* (2004) research in Sokoto implicated *Fusarium* sp., *Bipolaris* sp., *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* sp. This study's findings align with previous research conducted in various Nigerian regions. Onunka and Ekwenye (2000) in Port Harcourt isolated *Fusarium solani* from decaying Irish potato tubers. Similarly, Abdu *et al.* (2020) in Adamawa State implicated *Aspergillus flavus* and *Rhizopus stolonifer*. Ibrahim *et al.* (2014) in Sokoto State identified multiple fungi, including *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium* sp. Ogunsola and Aduramigba-Modupe (2014) in Abuja reported *Botryodiplodia* sp. and *Fusarium verticilloides* as causal agents. The fungi isolated from decaying Irish potato tubers in this study (*Bipolaris* sp., *Fusarium* sp. and *Aspergillus flavus*) have been previously identified in other tuber crops. Liamngee *et al.* (2015) found these fungi in decaying yam in Obudu, Cross River State. Gwa and Nwankiti (2018) isolated similar fungi in decaying yam tubers in Makurdi, Benue State. Eze and Ameh (2011) identified these fungi in decaying cocoyam. Variations in fungal species between studies may be attributed to geographical location, sample size, storage methods, harvesting techniques, sample specimen, collection source, climate, and postharvest handling.

According to Fayinminu *et al.* (2023), pathogenic organisms infiltrate tubers through harvesting-related injuries or natural openings like cracks and burrows on the surface. Okigbo *et al.* (2009) support this notion. Typically, fungi causing Irish potato rot are lesion pathogens, altering the tuber's consistency and rendering it unsuitable for consumption or significantly reducing market value. Furthermore, suboptimal storage conditions facilitate moisture absorption, fostering mold growth due to storage facility defects (Shukla *et al.*, 2012).

This study revealed significant variations in fungal occurrence across different locations. Irish potato tubers from Wurukum market exhibited the highest fungal incidence. Additionally, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp. and *Fusarium* sp. displayed disparate distribution patterns across locations. These disparities may be attributed to market sanitation, storage methods, tuber collection sources and postharvest handling practices. Our findings align with Mohammed *et al.* (2017) study in Kaduna, which reported varying distributions of *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium* sp., and *Fusarium* sp. across different markets.

The pathogenicity test revealed that *Bipolaris* sp. induced the highest rot on healthy Irish potato tubers, surpassing other fungi. This may be attributed to its nutrient utilization efficiency and virulence nature. Contrary to previous findings by Muhammed *et al.* (2017), Nwachukwu (2006), and Ibrahim *et al.* (2014), which reported *Rhizopus* species as the primary rot inducers, this study highlights *Bipolaris* sp. exceptional pathogenicity. All test fungi demonstrated pathogenicity, with variations in decay levels likely due to differences in nutrient utilization. Irish potato tubers' low pH, moisture content and nutritional composition make them susceptible to fungal infection (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2009). Postharvest losses pose significant challenges to food security.

Conclusion

This study identified *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bipolaris* sp. and *Fusarium* sp. as primary fungi responsible for postharvest decay of Irish potato tubers in Makurdi. Pathogenicity tests confirmed their ability to induce rot, with *Bipolaris* sp. exhibiting the highest severity. Wurukum market-sourced tubers showed the highest fungal incidence. Fungal colonization leads to reduced consumption quality, market value and potential mycotoxin production, posing health risks to consumers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Proper handling practices should be adopted by farmers and sellers to prevent harvest-related injuries that facilitate fungal invasion.
2. Good hygienic practices are essential to prevent inoculum transmission to produce post-harvest.
3. Irish potato tubers exhibiting symptoms of rot or fungal mycelia should be discarded to prevent consumption.

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